
HUMOUR AND SATIRE IN WILLIAM SHAKESPEARE'S COMEDIES

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ANNOTATSIYA

Uilyam Shekspir o'z davrining mashhur yozuvchisi edi. Uning asarlari millionlab kitobxonlar qalbidan joy olgan. U bir nechta janrlarda yozgan: tragediya, tarix va, albatta, komediya. Uilyam Shekspirning 39 ta pyesasini bilamiz, jumladan, boshqa dramaturglar bilan bir nechta hamkorlik.

Uilyam Shekspir nomi ko'pincha adabiyotdagi klassik dramalar, romantika va tragediyalar bilan bog'liq. Shekspirning o'z pyesalaridagi hazil va satira uchun ajoyib sovg'asi ko'pchilikni sog'inishi mumkin bo'lgan narsadir. Quyidagi maqolada Shekspirning komediya asarlaridagi satira va hazil tushunchalari haqida ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Shekspir, pyesalar, komediya, janr, yumor, satira.

ABSTRACT

William Shakespeare was a famous writer of his time. His works are in the hearts of millions of readers. He wrote in several genres: tragedy, history, and of course comedy. We know of 39 plays by William Shakespeare, including a few collaborations with other playwrights.

William Shakespeare's name is frequently connected to classic dramas, romance, and tragedy in literature. Shakespeare's extraordinary gift for humor and satire in his plays, however, is something that many people could miss. The following article provides information about the concepts of satire and humor in Shakespeare's comedic works.

Keywords: Shakespeare, plays, comedy, genre, humor, satire.

АБСТРАКТ

Уильям Шекспир был известным писателем своего времени. Его произведения находятся в сердцах миллионов читателей. Он писал в нескольких жанрах: трагедия, история и конечно комедия. Нам известно 39 пьес Уильяма Шекспира, включая несколько произведений, созданных в сотрудничестве с другими драматургами.

Имя Уильяма Шекспира часто связывают с классическими драмами, любовными романами и трагедиями в литературе. Однако выдающийся дар Шекспира к юмору и сатире в его пьесах – это то, что многие люди могли упустить. В следующей статье представлена информация о понятиях сатиры и юмора в комедийных произведениях Шекспира.

Ключевые слова: Шекспир, пьесы, комедия, жанр, юмор, сатира.

INTRODUCTION

Shakespeare's comedies have endured over time. literary works like "The Merchant of Venice". "Much Ado About Nothing" and "As You Like It" are two of the Bard's most well-known and often performed pieces. Some twelve or so of Shakespeare's plays are referred to be comedies, but they are not comedies in the contemporary sense of the word. Shakespearean comedies are not always pleasant or lighthearted, and their characters and plots are rarely extremely humorous. Shakespeare's comedy was, in fact, extremely different from comedy now. Shakespearean comedies have many of the same essential elements and styles as other Shakespearean genres, therefore it is not always easy to tell which of his plays is a comedy. Satire and humor have always been essential components of writing. Few authors have had as much of an influence in the comedy genre as William Shakespeare. His comedies, which are witty, word played, and cleverly blasted, still make audiences laugh. Shakespeare's comedies are renowned for their funny scenarios and carefree attitude. Shakespeare crafts complex tales that captivate and amuse audiences with witty wordplay, puns, and comedic timing. His

comedies frequently center on themes of love, misidentification, and social conventions, which creates a wealth of opportunity for humorous scenarios to occur. Wordplay is one of the most common humorous tricks Shakespeare employs. His characters create a lighthearted and amusing environment with their clever repartee and jokes. As in “Much Ado About Nothing”, for example.

FINDINGS

William Shakespeare was an English poet, actor, and playwright. He is universally recognized as the world’s finest dramatist and the best writer in the English language. He was born in April 26th, 1564, Stratford-upon-Avon, England. Shakespeare occupies a unique position in world literature. 39 plays, 154 sonnets, three lengthy narrative poems, and a few other lines, some of which are unclearly authored, make up his body of work that is now in existence, including collaborations. More plays by him than by any other author have been presented, and they have been translated into every major language spoken today. Shakespeare is still regarded as the most significant author in the English language, and scholars continue to analyze and reinterpret his writings. Shakespeare’s comedies are indeed a treasure trove of humor and satire, showcasing his keen wit and sharp observation of human nature. Here’s how humor and satire manifest in his comedies:

Wordplay and Wit: Shakespeare was a master of puns, wordplay, and clever repartee. Characters often engage in witty banter and exchange humorous insults. For example, in “Twelfth Night”, Sir Toby Belch and Sir Andrew Aguecheek’s antics provide ample opportunities for wordplay and comedic dialogue.

Comic Situations: Shakespeare’s comedies are filled with absurd situations, mistaken identities, and misunderstandings that lead to hilarious outcomes. In “A Midsummer Night’s Dream”, the antics of the Athenian lovers under the spell of Puck’s magic create chaos and comedic confusion in the forest.

Satirical Portrayals: Shakespeare often satirizes social norms, institutions, and conventions of his time. In “As You Like It”, he critiques the rigid social hierarchy

through the character of Touchstone, the witty court jester who provides biting commentary on the folly of courtly life.

Character Types: Shakespeare employs stock characters like the wise fool, the bumbling servant, and the pompous authority figure to create humor and satire. Characters like Falstaff in the “Henry IV” plays embody a blend of comedic buffoonery and sharp social critique.

Role Reversals and Cross-dressing: Gender roles are often satirized through cross-dressing and role reversals in Shakespeare’s comedies. In “Twelfth Night”, Viola disguises herself as a man, leading to comic misunderstandings and challenging societal expectations of gender roles.

Irony and Parody: Shakespeare frequently uses irony and parody to poke fun at literary conventions and cultural stereotypes. In “The Taming of the Shrew”, the relationship between Petruchio and Katherine is a parody of traditional courtship rituals, with Petruchio employing absurd methods to “tame” Katherine.

Happy Endings: Despite the satirical elements, Shakespeare’s comedies typically end with resolution and reconciliation. The laughter often serves as a means of highlighting the absurdity of human behavior while ultimately reaffirming the values of love, forgiveness, and harmony.

Malapropisms and Comic Language: Shakespeare often employs malapropisms, where characters unintentionally use the wrong word, leading to comedic misunderstandings. For instance, Dogberry’s misuse of words in “Much Ado About Nothing” (“Comparisons are odorous”) adds to the comedy of the play.

Farcical Elements: Farcical situations, characterized by exaggerated physical comedy and improbable scenarios, are common in Shakespeare’s comedies. In “The Comedy of Errors”, the mistaken identities of twin brothers and their servants lead to hilarious confusion and slapstick humor.

Social Commentary Through Fool Characters: Shakespeare frequently uses fool characters, such as Feste in “Twelfth Night” and the Fool in “King Lear”, to offer incisive social commentary disguised as jest. These characters often possess keen

insight into the flaws of the ruling class and provide astute observations amidst their humorous antics.

Cultural and Political Satire: Shakespeare's comedies often contain subtle critiques of contemporary cultural and political issues. In "The Merchant of Venice," the character of Shylock, a Jewish moneylender, can be seen as a commentary on anti-Semitism and the injustices of religious discrimination.

Meta-Theatrical Elements: Shakespeare occasionally includes meta-theatrical moments in his comedies, where characters acknowledge their existence within a play or comment on theatrical conventions. In "A Midsummer Night's Dream", the amateur actors' hilariously inept performance of "Pyramus and Thisbe" adds a layer of self-aware humor to the play-within-a-play.

Transformation and Reversal of Expectations: Shakespeare often subverts audience expectations and conventions to create comedic effects. In "The Merry Wives of Windsor", Falstaff's failed attempts at seducing Mistress Ford and Mistress Page result in his humiliation, reversing the typical power dynamics and providing comic satisfaction.

These examples illustrate the multifaceted ways in which Shakespeare employs humor and satire in his comedies, engaging audiences with laughter while also offering insightful commentary on the human condition and the society of his time.

Social Hierarchies and Class Conflict: Shakespeare often satirizes the rigidity of social hierarchies and the absurdities of class distinctions. In "Twelfth Night", the interactions between the aristocratic characters and the lower-class members, such as Sir Toby Belch and Maria, highlight the farcical nature of social conventions.

Carnavalesque Festivities: Many of Shakespeare's comedies feature festive settings, such as masquerades, feasts, and celebrations, where characters temporarily escape the constraints of societal norms. These carnivalesque elements create opportunities for comedic revelry and subversion of authority, as seen in the mischievous antics of characters like Puck in "A Midsummer Night's Dream".

Shakespeare's contemporaries' comedies are justified by their satirical goals because comedies are typically regarded as a "lower" genre than tragedies or historical fiction. Classical writers praised satire as a genre superior to other forms of comedy because it was ethically superior. City comedies had a moral purpose by making fun of the vices and foolishness of the day. Shakespeare was not particularly fond of current events satire. However, there is considerable evidence that Shakespeare's day did not adhere to the same standards and traditions when it came to comedy. Shakespeare's plays were not strictly categorized, as the title pages of the numerous quarto versions show. *Love's Labor's Lost* is billed as "A Pleasant Conceited Comedy" in its quarto edition (1598), while *Taming of the Shrew* is referred to as a "witty and pleasant comedy" in its quarto edition (1598). However, *The Merchant of Venice* (1600) is referred to as "The most excellent History of the Merchant of Venice" on its title page.

CONCLUSION

Overall, Shakespeare's comedies are a testament to his unparalleled ability to blend humor, wit, and social commentary, making them timeless classics that continue to entertain and resonate with audiences centuries later.

In conclusion, William Shakespeare's comedies stand as timeless masterpieces of wit, humor, and satire, captivating audiences with their linguistic virtuosity, comic characters, and insightful social commentary. Through a rich tapestry of verbal wit, irony, satire, and physical comedy, Shakespeare invites audiences to laugh, reflect, and ultimately, celebrate the absurdities of the human experience. As we continue to revisit and reinterpret Shakespeare's comedies, we are reminded of the enduring power of laughter and the universal truths that unite us all.

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